

USING GAMES WHILE TEACHING ENGLISH

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ANNOTATION

This article analyzes teaching methods through games as literary and stylistic device in Modern English language and its morphological characteristics.

Key words: *qualitative research, attractive structure, educational research, social constructivism, teaching analysis, games theory, qualitative methodologies*

English, a global language, has become one of the dominant mediums in politics, economy, and education internationally. English nowadays is the major medium to communicate with the whole world and the main language used for international trade and academic study. Accordingly, possessing basic English proficiency has become one of the essential requirements for many students. Also, in society there is an obviously positive correlation that the better a person's English ability, the greater that person's chances for higher education, professional employment and promotion prospects. The significance of English, therefore, cannot be ignored. Interest in using language games as teaching and learning activities in educational contexts is on the rise. The aim of this paper is to examine the use of communicative language games for teaching and learning English at academic lyceums. The instrument used in this study was a survey questionnaire about participants' perspectives on the use of communicative language games in English lessons. The results of the study provided encouraging evidence to indicate that foreign language teachers generally appreciated the benefits and value of communicative game activities in the teaching of English language. The findings also suggested that when facing students with different

backgrounds, learning styles, needs, and expectations, teachers should be aware to take learners' individual variations into account and be more flexible in their use of communicative games in order to maximize educational effect. It is hoped that communicative language games will attract more attention and will be applied more widely in the classroom with more positive attitudes on the part of language teachers.

The typical English teaching methods are form-based and text-based, and many teachers adopt Grammar Translation Method or Audiolingual Method on their teaching. English is taught by using dialogues for repetition and memorization, along with lots of systematic and intensive drills on sentence patterns and grammar rules. Grammar is regarded as the cornerstone in English instruction, whereas conversational English is hardly practiced. There is no real communication in English classes. Acquiring linguistic knowledge becomes the end instead of any ability to appropriately use the language of English. It is, therefore, often discovered that through such methods some students have fundamental understanding of formulaic phrases, but are unable or too shy to put them to use, not to mention the difficulties in conversing with a fluent speaker. For those students, English language is not a practical language in which they can freely communicate with others, but merely another subject for examinations.

The most frequently used games in teaching English.

The present study investigated the effects of teaching English through games. The findings of world experience are revealing that students are significantly improving in vocabulary knowledge and ability to communicate. Moreover, they are tending to have more positive attitudes towards learning English through games. Regarding these results, it can be recommended that using games in teaching English is beneficial to beginners especially those in primary school. However, to do so, teachers ought to consider thoughtfully when selecting suitable games to be used. This is because it was found in the study that students with different learning styles and English ability performed differently when different types of games were used.

In particular, students knowledge based of this level requires that students have to be able to exchange and present information in English and are able to integrate

speaking, listening and reading skills in order to communicate in particular topics such as, personal information, environment and hobbies. However, to be able to adopt a communicative approach into classes, teachers need to know and to familiarize with it; otherwise, they continue traditionally teaching style.

Games provide language teachers with many advantages when they are used in classroom. One of these advantages is that learners are motivated to learn the language when they are in a game. Scientists emphasize this point by suggesting that games automatically stimulate student interest, a properly introduced game can be one of the highest motivating techniques. They further argues that games spur motivation and students get very absorbed in the competitive aspects of the games; moreover, they try harder at games than in other courses. In other words, games stimulate students' interest in classroom activities and as a result, students become motivated and willing to learn.

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